

Spectrophotometric Studies of Uranium(VI) Complex with Rutin (Quercetin-3-rutinoside)

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Spectrophotometric studies of uranyl-rutin complex have been carried out. Uranium forms with rutin an orange, water-soluble complex which obeys Lambert-Beer's law at 445 m μ within the concentration range of 1.19-23.80 p.p.m. of uranium. The colour intensity of the complex does not vary between pH 4.8 and 7.0. The molar composition of the complex shows that it contains uranium and rutin in the molar ratio of 1:2. The stability constant of the complex has been determined by a method based on Beer's law.

Rutin has already been used for spectrophotometric determination of thorium¹ and titanium(IV)². The present work deals with spectrophotometric studies on the water-soluble, orange uranyl-rutin complex which is formed when an ethanolic solution of rutin is added to uranyl solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

An ethanolic solution (1×10^{-3} mole/litre) of pure rutin¹ was employed. A standard uranium solution was made from uranyl nitrate (A.R.). All other reagents employed were of A.R. quality.

Uvicam spectrophotometer, model S.P. 600, was employed for spectrophotometric measurements at 380-700 m μ . Absorption cells used were 1 cm thick. Beckman pH meter, model H2, with a suitable glass electrode was used for pH measurements.

Absorption Spectra.—The absorption spectrum of rutin in the visible region showed maximum absorption at 410 m μ . The absorption spectrum of uranium-rutin complex, when the reagent was employed as the reference solution, recorded a maximum at 445 m μ . All subsequent spectrophotometric studies of the complex were carried out at 445 m μ , as the absorption due to the reagent at this wave length was negligible. The absorption spectra of the complex at pH 2.0-9.0 showed the maximum at about 445 m μ in each case.

Effect of Excess of Reagent on Optical Density of the Complex.—The optical densities at 445 m μ of a series of solutions containing rutin and uranium in the molar ratios of 0.5:1 to 9:1 were determined. The results show that the absorption due to the complex remains constant, when the mole ratio is 6 and above. The molar ratio of the reagent to uranium was, however, maintained at 10 in subsequent estimations. An excess of the reagent did not affect the optical density of the complex.

Effect of pH on Uranium-rutin Complex.—It was found that the absorption by the complex remained constant in the pH range 4.8-7.0 (Fig. 1). The pH of uranyl solution was adjusted with 0.1N-NaOH and 0.1N-HCl.

1. Dev and Jain, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1962, 4, 286.
2. *Idem*, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1962, 190, 316.

Stability of the Colour of the Complex.—The colour of the complex was found stable for 48 hrs. The complex was found to obey Lambert-Beer's law at $445m\mu$ for the concentration range of 1.19 to 23.80 p.p.m. of uranium.

Interference due to Foreign Ions.—Oxalate, tartrate, fluoride, aluminium, copper, iron, ceric, thorium, titanium, vanadium, zirconium, and molybdenum ions even in minute quantities were found to interfere. Large quantities of acetate, phosphate, borate, citrate, chloride, bromide, iodide, sulphate, nickel, lead, cobalt, manganese, cerous, lanthanum and beryllium had no effect.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2. x ml of P -molar rutin soln. added to $(10-x)$ ml of P -molar uranyl nitrate.

Molar Composition of the Complex.—Molar composition of the uranyl complex, as determined by Job's method,³ modified by Vosburgh and Cooper⁴, employing concentrations of (a) $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ and (b) $1.25 \times 10^{-3} M$ (Fig. 2) shows that the reagent and uranium are present in the complex in the ratio of 2:1.

The molar composition of the uranium complex was verified by the slope-ratio method⁵. For this purpose, two series of solutions were prepared, employing $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ solutions of rutin and of uranium. In one series, the uranium concentration was varied maintaining the concentration of the rutin constant and in sufficient excess and in the other, rutin concentration was varied maintaining the uranium concentration constant and in sufficient excess. The optical densities of the solutions of both these series were determined at $445m\mu$ with ethanol as reference. The observed values are plotted as curves P and Q in Fig. 3; the straight line portions AB and CD, respectively, of these curves are taken into account to find out the slopes:

3. *Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 8, 113.4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437.5. Harvey and Manning, *ibid.*, 1950, 72, 4488.

FIG. 3

$\tan \theta_1 = \text{slope of the curve P (AB)} = 0.55$

$\tan \theta_2 = \text{slope of the curve Q (CD)} = 0.25$

Molar ratio of the complex $= \frac{0.55}{0.25} = 2.2$

Curve P: x ml of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ uranyl soln. added to 10 ml of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ rutin soln. and vol. made to 15 ml with EtOH.

Curve Q: x ml of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ rutin soln. added to 10 ml of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ uranyl soln. and vol. made to 15 ml with EtOH.

Stability Constant of the Complex.—The stability constant of the complex was determined by the method based on Beer's law as adopted by Foley and Anderson⁶ for uranyl-sulphosalicylate complex. Two solutions of uranyl-rutin complex were prepared so that optical densities of both were either equal or nearly so, but contained different concentrations of metal ions and the complexing agent. In this way, pairs of such solutions were made. Since the dissociation constant is the same for members of a given pair, concentrations of the complex and thus the value of K may be calculated from the relation:

$$K = \frac{(MK_e)}{[C_{M_1} - (MK_e)] [CK_{e_1} - 2(MK_e)]^2}$$

$$= \frac{(MK_e)}{[C_{M_2} - (MK_e)] [CK_{e_2} - 2(MK_e)]^2}$$

where C_M 's and C_{K_e} 's are the initial concentrations of uranyl and rutin respectively and (MK_e) denotes the concentration of the complex produced. The ionic strength of the solutions was maintained at a constant value by addition of potassium nitrate ($0.5M$) and the optical density measurements were made at $445m\mu$. The average value of $\log K$ from several determinations at 20° was found to be 9.35.

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